

Pain is regarded as the fifth vital sign according to the Royal College of Anaesthetists and the Royal College of Surgeons[1].

This means that it should be included in the monitoring and performing of vital signs. A vital sign can be used by the clinician to check the status of a patient's health. It can also be used to assess pain.

Everyone experiences pain at some point in their lives. According to The International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) defines pain as “an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with, or resembling that associated with, actual or potential tissue damage” (Raja et al., 2020) [2].

When performing vital signs, a pain score should always be performed, because it is an essential element of vital signs monitoring and is the fifth vital sign.

The importance of pain assessment is acknowledged by the medical community as a vital part of the care of critically ill patients. It can help identify the cause of the pain and provide effective interventions.

A literature review by McAuliffe et al. (2008) identified barriers to successful pain assessment in older adults with dementia. The barriers identified included a lack of recognition, insufficient education, and pain assessment tools not being routinely used[3].

improve your techniques of patient education and empowerment as first steps to ensure uniform and effective pain management.

Ref:

- 1- Schiavo JH. Oral health literacy in the dental office: the unrecognized patient risk factor. *J Dent Hyg.* 2011;85(4):248–255.
- 2- Horowitz AM, Maybury C, Kleinman DV, et al. Health literacy environmental scans of community-based dental clinics in Maryland. *Am J Public Health.* 2014;104(8):e85–e93.
- 3- Roett MA, Coleman MT. Practice improvement, part II: health literacy. *FP Essent.* 2013;414:19–24.